

Contribution of Khayal Gharanas to Indian Classical Music

Prof. Aniruddha Sanjay Dalvi

Assistant Professor, Department of Music,

Sitabai Arts, Commerce and Science College, Akola

Corresponding Author- Prof. Aniruddha Sanjay Dalvi

Abstract-

Indian classical music is an integral part of Indian music. The tradition of Indian classical music goes back to Bharat Muni's Natyashastra and before that the singing of Samaveda. Bharat Natya Shastra, written by Bharat Muni, is considered to be the first written evidence of the history of Indian music. There are many differences of opinion regarding the time of its composition. Many aspects of today's Indian classical music are mentioned in this ancient text. After Bharat Muni's Natyashastra, Matanga Muni's Brihaddeshi and Sharangdev's Sangeet Ratnakar are considered to be the most important texts from the historical point of view. Later Sufi movement also had its influence on Indian music. Later, many new systems and gharanas were born in different parts of the country. During the British rule, many new instruments came into vogue and Indian music was also introduced to Western music. The harmonium, the instrument popular today among the general public, came into use at the same time. In this way, every era had its important contribution in the rise and change of Indian music. Instruments commonly used in Hindustani music include sitar, sarod, surbahar, israj, veena, tanpura, bansuri, shehnai, sarangi, violin, santoor, pakhwaj and tabla. Instruments commonly used in Carnatic music include Veena, Vinu, Gotavadam, Harmonium, Mridangam, Kanjir, Ghamat, Nadashwaram and violin.

Key words: - Indian classical music, Gharana system, Khayal, Dhruvapada.

Introduction:-

The Hindustani classical music has a rich tradition of Gharanas. In the music world, the word 'gharana' means 'Ghar' means lineage and Gharana means lineage-musical characteristics. When a talented musician with the influence of his creative power introduces a new vocal skill or style which his descendants and disciples follow, then those characteristics become a symbol of the rasa of that family. It gradually becomes established as a family. The meaning of Gharana is the passing on of certain characteristics from generation to generation, that is, the Guru-disciple tradition is called Gharana. It is believed that the formation of Gharana through singing is like a singer made some disciples and he made some more disciples, in this way the generations of disciples continued, which was called Gharana. The popular Gharanas that have become famous are Gwalior Gharana, Kirana Gharana, Agra Gharana, Jaipur Gharana. Patiala Gharana, Bhendbazar Gharana, Rampur Gharana, Mewati Gharana. Indian Music was divided into two parts, North Indian Music and South Indian Music. North Indian is called Hindustani Music and South Indian as the Carnatic Music. Pt. Bhatkhande said, 'There is no denying that the North Indian music of that time needed some important changes and these were provided by the advent of foreign music.'¹ 'During British reign, Indian Classical music got no support from British Government, due to which quality and quantity of Indian classical music started decreasing. Britishers were never interested in promotion of art and culture of India hence they never gave any patronization to any artist, due to which, lots of good artists get discouraged.'²

Contribution of Khayal Gharanas to Indian Classical Music:

Word 'Khayal' is derived from Persian means "idea or imagination". Origin of this Khayal style was attributed to Amir Khusrau. It is also referred to as a 'Bandish'. Khayal is composed in a particular raga and tala and has a brief text. Texts mainly include Praise of kings, Pranks of Lord Krishna, Divine love & Sorrow of separation. Major Gharanas in Khayal are Gwalior, Kirana, Patiala, Agra, and Bhendibazaar Gharana. Gwalior Gharana is the oldest and considered the mother of all other gharanas. The word Gharana means Ghar which means 'of the house'⁴. The word Gharana has many meanings Ghar, Kutumb, Parivar, Sampardaye, Vansh Prampara etc. It refers to a family of musicians, a school of music or a musical lineage connected by the name of a particular person or place. The characteristic feature of a Gharana is the special style of teaching. According to Dr. Krish "A tradition of the intellect of Gurus, and generations of guru shishya parampara all of these together make a Gharana.'³ Gharana, in Hindustani music stands for 'A community of performers and who share a distinctive musical style to a particular instructor or region. The emergence of Gharana system has its roots in the Guru-Shishya Parampara which is the hallmark of learning traditional art. A gharana indicates a comprehensive musicological ideology. This ideology changes from one gharana to another. It directly affects the thinking, teaching, performance of music.

The Khayal was the next step of evolution in Indian classical Music after Dhruvad. Dhruvad came into existence in the 14th century. Legendary Gopal Nayak, Baiju Bawara, Swami Haridas and Tansen are considered to be its main personalities. Khayal,

classical form of modern times is a unique form of Hindustani Classical Music. The word Khayal means, whim, imagination or Kalpana.⁴ this word came to India with the Persian Language. Khayal implies the idea of verse which is imaginative and conceptual in its nature. The term Khayal suggests the ideas of imagination and imaginative composition and from the meaning it can further be inferred that the Khayal is imaginative in conception, artistic and decorative in execution and romantic in appeal. "The Khayal of today, though based on Dhrupada, was a revolt against the Dhrupada itself which was too rigid, mechanical and losing its aesthetic appeal."⁵ Beginning of the earliest times, there have always different schools of music in our country. "In the ancient period, the word used for gharana was 'samuday'. During the times old dhrupad, the word 'bani' came into vogue and after the advent of the Khayal, the concept of Gharana came into light. In this way the presence of different classes originated in Hindustani Music."⁶ "During the medium ages, singers got allocated in various kingdoms like Gwalior, Rampur, Udaipur, Lucknow, Baroda, and they practiced and propagated their own style of music. But due to lack of awareness they considered themselves to be the greatest. They instructed their disciples not to share the knowledge to the other people and keep it to themselves. This led to the formation of various Gharanas over time."⁷

Gwalior Gharana was created by Nathan Pir Baksh who was patronized by Gwalior-Naresh Jayaji Rao, the king of Gwalior State. This Gharana originated from Abdullah Khan and Kadir Bux Khan, who were brothers. They were deemed singers of Khayals and considered Ustads. In the singing of Gwalior Gharana, the progression of notes is simple. Serious type of singing is the big identity of this gharana. Behind the serious type of identity is to play with traditional restrictions. The taans introduced in the middle of any raga are also presented with great variety in this gharana. Music emperor Vishnu Digambar Paluskar was from this gharana. The Gharana system has played a great role in the creation and maintenance of our musical tradition. Gharanas existed all over India. Prominent Artists of this Gharana are Pandit Balkrishan Ichalkaranjkar, Pandit Vishnu Paluskar, Nissar Hussain Khan, Shri. Shankar Rao Pandit, Shri. Krishna Rao Shankar, Shri. Rajabhaya Punchwale, Bhaiya Ganpat Rao, Shri. B.R. Deodhar, and Shri. Natayan Rao Vya.

Agra Gharana has given an extremely evolved legacy of music. The Agra gharana's Ustad Ghulam abbas Khan was master of Alapa, Dhruvapada, Dhamar and Khayal. He was also a very hardworking teacher and trained three people mainly. They were Nathan Khan, his younger brother Kallan Khan and Faiyaz Khan, who

established himself as one of the finest musicians and made the Agra Gharana widely recognized as one of the best in the country. Nathan Khan's two sons namely Abdullah Khan and Vilayat Hussain Khan made a name in the field of Classical Music. After them Ustad Faiyaz Khan was gifted with a majestic yet melodious voice. He was a unique artist as he combined most of the righteousness of a vocalist. The Agra gharana absorbed attractive features from other gharanas and yet maintained its own inherent characteristics. "It must be remarked that this particular gharana pertains to vocal music only, and has no counterpart in instrumental music, and that it has had a specific style in Dhrupad, Dhamar and Khayal."⁸ Pandit Bhimsen Joshi, who was awarded Bharat Ratna, was from a kirana family. Singer Abdul Qarib Khan is considered to be the representative of Kirana Gharana. The great artist Sawai Gandharva also belonged to the Kirana family. In the singing of this gharana, Meend and Gamak are produced like the notes of Veena. The practice of tunes is the identity of the artists of this gharana. This is the identity of Kirana singing. Renowned and world renowned artists like Heerabai Barodkar, Gangubai Hangal and Prabha Atre have taken the tradition of Kirana Gharana far ahead. Kirana gharana have been influenced by Sufism as well as Carnatic music. The Kirana gharana were essentially Sarangi players which laid huge leverage in their style of performance. Ustad Abdul Karim Khan who can be called the most substantial member to have contributed wholeheartedly to make Kirana gharana stand where it is today. The Jaipur Gharana is a Khayal-based Gharana founded by Ustad Alladiya Khan in the late 19th century. This Gharana is also nearly 150 years old. "By the sole effort of Ustad Alladdiya Khan, the Jaipur- Gharana has also incorporated further facets to their style. This school of music however, strictly goes by the book, with implementation of Laya and rhythm, with elaboration, intricateness and complexity being stressed on all the three octaves."⁹

Ustad Dilawar Hussain Khan and his three sons, Ustad Chhajjoo Khan, Ustad Nazeer Khan and Ustad Khadim Hussain Khan are the Founders of Bhendi bazaar Gharana. The three brothers developed their own style and gained reputation as singers from "Bhendibazaar" and their style was called "Bhendibazaar Gayaki"¹⁰ Patiala Gharana has come into exist by excelled Ustad Bade Ghulam Ali Khan. The prominent Artists of Patiala Gharana are Ustad Bade Fateh Ali Khan, Ustad Ali Baksh Khan, Ustad Bade Ghulam Ali Khan, Munawwar Ali Khan, Abbas Ali Khan, Shri. Ajoy Chakraborty. Rampur Sahaswan also has special importance among the gharanas of Indian classical music. Singer Ustad Inayat Hussain Khan is considered to be its representative. In this gharana, the artists take

the lead in singing with each note. The artists of Rampur Sahaswan, who started the Aalap with Bandish, have paid a lot of attention to the literature of Bandish. Apart from Ustad Inayat Khan, Ustad Ghulam Mustafa Khan, Ustad Nisar Hussain Khan and Rashid Khan are the prominent singers of this gharana. Rashid Khan is one of the most renowned classical singers of the country at present. He has taken classical singing to great heights. Rampur Gharana, was established by Inayat Hussain Khan. Inayat Hussain Khan was the son of Ustad Mehboob Khan, a Khayal singer and Veena player of the Rampur court. Inayat Hussain Khan was a disciple of Bahadur Hussain Khan. This gharana is regarded as an offshoot of the Gwalior Gayaki. The Mewati Gharana was founded by Ustad Ghagge Nazir Khan Sahib. From its foundation 6 generations have contributed for the progress of Mewat Gharana.

Conclusion:-

A Gharana is a system of social organization linking musicians to a particular musical style. Although there are stylistic differences, the basic elements of swara, raga and tala as the foundation of both Carnatic and Hindustani. Hindustani music originated in the Vedic period and Carnatic music originated during the Bhakti movement. The Agra gharana is associated with Ustad Faiyaz, the Gwalior gharana is associated with Ustad Haddu Khan and Ustad Alladiya Khan. Haddu Khan, the Jaipur gharana is associated with Ustad Alladiya Khan's disciple Ustad Nathu Khan and his son Ustad Mallikarjun Mansur, the Kirana gharana is associated with Ustad Abdul Karim Khan and these musicians and teachers continue to inspire and influence musicians around the world. The Gharana system has a great contribution to the Hindustani Classical Music. It becomes clear that Gharana proved to be very important in keeping our cultural and social traditions strong and in furthering the development and usefulness of the society and in teaching human discipline, restraint and reverence for ancestors etc. In each gharana, the style of singing and playing was especially preserved in the form of disciples, whose utility/imprint is clearly visible like a seal on every disciple of that gharana. It was only through these disciples or musicians that the glimpse of ancient music could reach us.

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